

FORMULATION OF *FIBER*-FAILURE CRITERIA, FOR FIBER-POLYMER COMPOSITES, IN TERMS OF STRAIN INVARIANTS

John Hart-Smith and Jon Gosse

*Phantom Works, Long Beach, California, and Seattle, Washington
The Boeing Company*

SUMMARY: An analogy is drawn between the first author's works on fiber-dominated strengths of fiber-polymer composites through a generalization of the Tresca (maximum-shear-stress) criterion and the second author's model for predicting matrix failures in terms of strain invariants. First, Gosse's model is applied to glass fibers, because they are isotropic, like resin matrices, and the theory can be applied without needing any changes. These models apply to the fiber and matrix *constituents* of composite laminates. The invariant model is then extended to failures in carbon fibers, which are not isotropic and which require multiple Young's moduli and Poisson's ratios for characterizing stresses. It is proposed here that these variable properties have absolutely no effect on the invariant failure criteria when formulated in terms of *strains*. At the lamina level, this reformulation of the fiber-failure criteria in terms of the von Mises' shear strain is shown to be almost identical, numerically, with Hart-Smith's earlier formulation in terms of the Tresca criterion. New unambiguous experimental confirmation of this model is provided. The end result of this work is that the strength of fibers embedded in resin matrices can now be characterized in terms of only two failure mechanisms, dilatation (brittle fracture) and distortion (shear failure), with only two universal properties regardless of the states of deformation. (The effects of fiber waviness in woven layers is covered elsewhere; here, only unidirectional tape laminae are addressed.) It is important *not* to interact *any* of these distinct failure mechanisms, even though many other theories have assumed the existence of such interactions in the past. Likewise, it is shown here that there is absolutely no justification for the other traditional false assumption, that fibers and resin can be represented as a homogeneous "equivalent" composite material with the goal of thereby halving the number of properties needed. It is vital to understand that there is no such thing as a "composite material", only a composite *of* materials!

KEYWORDS: Composites, strength, fiber failures, matrix failures, strain invariants.

INTRODUCTION

In earlier papers on the strength of fiber-polymer composites, Hart-Smith presented and justified physics-based models for those portions of the failure envelope defined by *fiber* failures under arbitrary biaxial stresses. These unique models agreed with available test data, and were very easy to use. However, they could be applied only to well-designed laminates, i.e., those that did not fail prematurely in the matrix. Only experience could identify inferior laminates; these models couldn't.

Now, the first author has a partner who complemented these fiber-failure characterizations by a physics-based model for *matrix* failures characterized in terms of strain invariants (Ref. 1). At the failure-initiation level, Gosse's model involves only two strain invariants that seem to be remarkably similar in form to Hart-Smith's *fiber*-failure model, which also involves only two distinct failure mechanisms. For glass-fiber-reinforced laminates, the similarity between Gosse's invariant model and Hart-Smith's earlier model is as great as between the von Mises and Tresca models for yielding of ductile isotropic metals. (A third matrix property is needed to characterize nonlinear matrix behavior and possible damage progression, but there is no equivalent of this for fibers that lose their load-bearing capacity as soon as they have broken.)

The prime purpose of this paper is to reformulate Hart-Smith's earlier works based on the Tresca model (Ref. 2) in terms of the same strain invariants as Gosse used for matrix failures, first for isotropic glass fibers and, second, to generalize this model to non-isotropic carbon fibers. In this new form, based on the von Mises criterion, the fiber-failure model can be integrated into the *same* computer code Gosse had prepared for matrix failures. Another reason for this reformulation is to

improve the *comprehension* of Hart-Smith's fiber-failure model, in terms of a *single* property for all stress combinations. Nevertheless, the use of the original maximum-strain model for fiberglass-polymer laminates and for the truncated maximum-strain failure model for carbon-fiber reinforcement as simple empirical lamina-level models for fiber-dominated structures¹ continues to be justified.

THE STRAIN-INVARIANT CHARACTERIZATION OF MATRIX FAILURES

Gosse's matrix-failure model, at the initiation level, involves *only two mechanisms*. The most frequent failure mechanism is *dilatation*, in which an increase in volume leads to fracture of the polymer on a face perpendicular to the maximum principal strain. This would seem to be directly equivalent to the brittle fracture of fibers under dominant tensile axial loads, possibly influenced by minor additional stress or strain components. The second matrix-failure mechanism is by *distortion*, which needs to be dominated by compressive and or shear loads to prevent the dilatation failure mechanism from occurring first. The key feature of Hart-Smith's fiber-failure model that distinguishes it from earlier works is the claim that fiber failure can be based on a generalization in the strain plane of the Tresca criterion, which is, of course, a distortion-based model.

Gosse's matrix-failure model, depicted in Figure 1, consists of an infinite circular cylinder defining distortion failures that is unbounded for equal triaxial compression, indicating that failure is not possible then. The opposite end of the cylinder in the tension-dominated region is truncated by a flat surface, perpendicular to the axis, defining failures by dilatation, a totally different and unrelated mechanism. The application of Gosse's matrix-failure model has been to polymers between closely packed fibers within a ply, or to the thin resin layer between plies or bonded adherends.

Fig. 1 Gosse's Matrix Failure Criteria for Fiber-Polymer Composites

The 2-D cross-section shown through this 3-D failure envelope has the form of an ellipse with one end cut off, as shown in the inset in the upper-left corner of Figure 1. Given that the form of this shape is established by *two* different mechanisms, it is not really surprising that earlier attempts, by others, to concoct a distorted ellipse to model these phenomena in terms of a *single* variable have not been successful. In theory, if the dilatation strength were high enough and the resistance to distortion low enough, the complete failure envelope could be defined by the distortional failure mechanism. However, experience in interpreting actual test data for various fiber-polymer composites has shown that *both* failure mechanisms are involved, with dilatational matrix failures dominating.

Gosse's characterization of the dilatation cut-off in Figure 1 is the first strain invariant J_1 , which is a very close approximation of the increase in volume for small strains. That is

$$J_1 = \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 \quad (1)$$

As an invariant, there is no difference between the sum of these orthogonal strains with the reference

¹ These two very useful failure models have always needed to have *false* predictions of matrix failures, which have plagued so many other models, over-ridden. They have, however, been equally incapable of predicting *real* matrix failures that result from impact damage and which can occur in laminates with fibers in two few directions to constrain matrix deformations.

axes. This sum is related to the more commonly used strain-at-failure under a single stress in the 1 direction by the formula

$$J_1 = \varepsilon_1(1 - 2\nu) \quad . \quad (2)$$

Gosse's characterization of the distortional portion of the failure envelope in Figure 1 can be expressed by the shear strain equivalent to the well-known von Mises' shear stress²

$$\gamma_{\text{crit}} = \sqrt{\frac{(\varepsilon_1' - \varepsilon_2')^2 + (\varepsilon_1' - \varepsilon_3')^2 + (\varepsilon_2' - \varepsilon_3')^2}{2}} \quad . \quad (3)$$

The most general expression for this shear strain involves the components of shear strain as well³, except for axes aligned with the principal strain directions, identified by primed values. These reference axes are used here for simplicity of the derivations, but the complete expression can be substituted at any point, enabling the very different effects of applied *transverse* shear stresses acting on the fibers to be accounted for. For example. For a uniaxial load, this shear strain is equated to the direct strain by the equation

$$\gamma_{\text{crit}} = (1 + \nu)\varepsilon_{1\text{crit}}' \quad . \quad (4)$$

Gosse's theory really is as simple as this, even though its application is always improved by including in these strain components the strains equivalent to the residual thermal stresses developed during cool-down of fiber-polymer composites after cure at elevated temperatures. In some situations, it is *necessary* to include these thermal strains, because they can be so much larger than the applied mechanical strains. However, provided that the matrix is always very much softer than the fibers, as is usually the case for polymer resins, the corresponding thermally induced stresses in the fibers will be negligible in comparison with the stresses resulting from mechanical loads. For this reason, the treatment of residual thermal stresses by Gosse, (at Hart-Smith's instigation) is not discussed here, even though they are included in his existing computer codes for both matrix and fiber strengths. Analyses have confirmed that the influence of residual thermal stresses in the fibers is insignificant.

The preceding equations seem to imply that uniform states of stress and strain exist in the matrix. This is no more true for the resin than it is for fibers. At Hart-Smith's instigation, Gosse has prepared micro-mechanical finite-element models with which to characterize the non-uniform strains in the resin, and the fibers, in terms of the lamina-level strains generated by traditional finite-element analyses of complete structures. These universal models generate strain amplification factors that are employed during post-processing without complicating the basic analysis. The criteria are applied at the most critical locations. There is no averaging of conditions throughout any finite volumes. These analyses have shown that the matrix strains are sensitive to the fiber volume, but not very sensitive to fiber array (hexagonal, square, diamond, for example). Experience has identified two likely locations for the most critical conditions to develop. One is in the middle of the interstices between clusters of three or four fibers, and the other is between adjacent pairs of fibers, where they are the closest. The strain invariants reach local (stationary) maxima there, simplifying the finite-element solutions. The axial stresses in the fibers tend to be fairly uniform, but there is a great variation in the distribution of *transverse* stresses and strains that needs to be accounted for. Nevertheless, this issue of *applying* the models in the presence of non-uniformity can be separated from the *formulation* of the theories, which is the issue studied here.

THE STRAIN-INVARIANT CHARACTERIZATION OF FAILURES IN ISOTROPIC GLASS FIBERS

Because glass fibers are isotropic, like resin matrices, the characterization of their strength in terms of these same invariants should be the same. *Two* failure mechanisms are possible, one by dilatation,

² Gosse actually uses the words "*equivalent* shear strain" to describe this same quantity for the isotropic resin matrix, because so many of his customers had difficulty thinking of the von Mises criterion in any form other than as *stress* components or of strains other than as the tensorial components. It is an invariant in the sense that this measure of distortion is independent of the reference axes; it is actually the second deviator of strain.

³
$$\gamma_{\text{crit}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} [(\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2)^2 + (\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_3)^2 + (\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_3)^2] + \frac{3}{4} [\gamma_{12}^2 + \gamma_{13}^2 + \gamma_{23}^2]} \quad .$$

usually under almost pure axial tensile stress because the soft matrix does not allow any other tensile stress components of comparable intensity to develop, and the other by distortion, which usually occurs under axial compression loads for the same reason but which requires, in addition, that the fibers be sufficiently well stabilized that they do not fail by some form of instability first. The real question is which mechanism dominates when. Extensive testing of dry fibers has confused this issue since, then, the fibers most frequently fail at flaws. However, when embedded in resin in laminates, only the very first fibers to fail may initiate failures at flaws. When the laminate finally fails, virtually all of the fibers fail where there *aren't* any flaws! What is the mechanism of failure in glass fibers fail *away* from any flaws – dilatation or distortion? Testing of individual fibers can never solve this riddle. But, given that there are only two mechanisms available, we can make predictions for each, at the lamina and laminate level, and see which best matches the observations.

In applying the criteria in Equations (1) and (3) to glass fibers, it *must* be remembered that these equations apply at the *constituent* (fiber) level and not necessarily in terms of strains at the lamina level. Obviously, except at free edges, the strain in the matrix is the same as that along the *length* of the fibers. However, it was shown by the simple micromechanical models in Ref. 3 that even the average *transverse* strain in the lamina is greater than five times that in the fiber. This has a great bearing on how Equation (1) is depicted – and comprehended.

The basic strain-stress relations for isotropic solids, in the three principal directions, are

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_1' \\ \varepsilon_2' \\ \varepsilon_3' \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E} & -\frac{\nu}{E} & -\frac{\nu}{E} \\ -\frac{\nu}{E} & \frac{1}{E} & -\frac{\nu}{E} \\ -\frac{\nu}{E} & -\frac{\nu}{E} & \frac{1}{E} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1' \\ \sigma_2' \\ \sigma_3' \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

For conventional laminated fiber-polymer composites, it is usual that the stress normal to the plane of the laminae be zero. It is customary that this be the stress designated in the 3-direction. In the context of Equations (5), with $\sigma_3 \equiv 0$, the strain invariant J_1 in Equation (1) would be expressed as

$$J_1 = \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 = \frac{(1-2\nu)}{E} (\sigma_1' + \sigma_2') \quad (6)$$

If the embedded fibers failed under uniaxial load at a strain of ε_L^\dagger , the critical value of the strain invariant would be

$$J_1 = (1-2\nu)\varepsilon_L^\dagger, \quad (7)$$

just as in Equation (2) for the matrix. If transverse tensile stress were applied to the glass fibers, the critical strain ε_L^\dagger would be reduced by such biaxial loads, but not by very much since, in Equation (6), the longitudinal *fiber* (not lamina) strength of some 500 ksi would be reduced by no more than the 10 ksi or so that typical resin matrices could apply, even if no allowance is made for the poor adhesion between the fibers and resin. On the fiber strain plane, the locus of biaxial strains matching the critical J_1 value would be a straight line, sloping at -45° , as shown in Figure 2. However, on the corresponding *lamina* strain plane, the slope would be increased by a factor of at least five (for which the slope would be -79°), which is also shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 Dilatational Portion of Glass-Fiber Failure Criteria, on Fiber and Lamina Strain Planes

For the second of Gosse's invariant criteria, for failure by excessive distortion, Equation (3), can be applied directly to isotropic glass fibers, with no need for change. It is best known in the form of stresses, rather than strains, as shown in the classic von Mises' ellipse in Figure 3.

The quantities needed to evaluate this critical shear strain, in the customary absence of stress in the 3 direction, can be evaluated from Equations (5) as follows.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_1' - \varepsilon_2' \\ \varepsilon_1' - \varepsilon_3' \\ \varepsilon_2' - \varepsilon_3' \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{(1+\nu)}{E} & -\frac{(1+\nu)}{E} \\ \frac{(1+\nu)}{E} & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{(1+\nu)}{E} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1' \\ \sigma_2' \end{Bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 3 The von Mises Criterion on the Constituent Plane

For isotropic glass fibers, as a constituent of typical composite laminates, Equation (3) can now be evaluated explicitly from Equations (8).

$$\gamma_{\text{crit}} = \frac{(1+\nu)}{E} \sqrt{\frac{(\sigma_1' - \sigma_2')^2 + (\sigma_1')^2 + (\sigma_2')^2}{2}} \quad (9)$$

For uniaxial tension or compression at a stress level σ_0 , in the 1 or 2 direction separately,

$$\gamma_{\text{crit}} = \pm \frac{(1+\nu)}{E} \sigma_0 = (1+\nu)\varepsilon_0 \quad (10)$$

For equal biaxial stress in the same directions applied simultaneously, Equation (9) would now predict the very same result, as is consistent with Figure 3.

For equal-and-opposite stresses, of magnitude $\sigma_0/\sqrt{3} = 0.577\sigma_0$, the very same result is predicted again. These results are plotted in Figure 4, on the strain plane, with the circumscribing ellipse corresponding exactly with that shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 4 The von Mises and Tresca Criteria on the Fiber Constituent Strain Plane

The von Mises and Tresca criterion predict exactly the same result for equal uniaxial and for biaxial stresses of the same sign, but slightly different stresses and strains for equal-and-opposite loads.

In Figure 4, the Tresca criterion is what Hart-Smith applied to characterizing the strength of fibers, while the von Mises criterion is what Gosse used in his invariant model for the strength of the matrix when it failed by distortion. The form of the two failure envelopes is remarkably similar, just as for ductile metal alloys.

The converse set of equations to Equations (3), expressing principal stresses as functions of principal strains, is

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1' \\ \sigma_2' \\ \sigma_3' \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{1}{(1-\nu^2)} \begin{bmatrix} E & \nu E & \nu E \\ \nu E & E & \nu E \\ \nu E & \nu E & E \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_1' \\ \varepsilon_2' \\ \varepsilon_3' \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (11)$$

from which, if there is no normal stress (i.e. $\sigma_3' = 0$),

$$(\sigma_1' - \sigma_2') = \frac{E}{(1+\nu)} (\varepsilon_1' - \varepsilon_2') . \quad (12)$$

Equation (9) can now be expressed in its more basic form, for glass fibers embedded in soft polymer matrices,

$$\gamma_{\text{crit}} = \pm(\varepsilon_1' - \varepsilon_2') \quad \text{for } \sigma_3' = 0, \quad (13)$$

which is *exactly* the relation Hart-Smith used in his first characterization of shear failures in fibers embedded in soft resin matrices in such papers as Ref. 4. Rotation of the reference axes on the plane of zero stress enables the two companion equations to be established.

$$\gamma_{\text{crit}} = \pm(\varepsilon_1' - \varepsilon_3') \quad \text{for } \sigma_2' = 0, \quad \text{and } \gamma_{\text{crit}} = \pm(\varepsilon_2' - \varepsilon_3') \quad \text{for } \sigma_1' = 0. \quad (14), (15)$$

It is now clear that, for *glass* fibers at least, there is absolutely no significant difference between Hart-Smith's characterization of shear failures in fibers and Gosse's characterization of distortional failures in the matrix between the fibers, other than that, in the new formulation, the minor effects of the limited shear stresses *applied* to the fibers can also be accounted for, just as direct and shear strain components have always been combined in each strain invariant in Gosse's work on matrix failures.

It seems plausible to establish the value of this critical shear strain experimentally by uniaxial compression of a *block* of glass that needs no stabilization. If the compression strain reached this way were given by $-\varepsilon_B^C$, the critical shear strain would be given by Equation (12) as

$$\gamma_{\text{crit}} = \pm(1+\nu)\varepsilon_B^C. \quad (16)$$

If an attempt were made to measure this property on an axially compressed block of fiber-polymer composite, it is far more likely that some lower strain, $-\varepsilon_L^C$ would be established. This is *not* a fiber property alone; it is the limit defined by fiber waviness or by the matrix no longer being able to stabilize compressed fibers. It is commonly established empirically, the process being complicated by variability resulting from fiber wash in thick blocks of parallel plies and by the minor or pronounced crimping in different woven fabrics. Such a failure limit would appear on Figure 4 as a sloping line, for which $\sigma_1 = \text{constant}$, that truncated the left side of the figure, *without* changing anything else in it.

Figure 4 is plotted on the *fiber* strain plane. If these same conditions had been plotted on the unidirectional *lamina* strain plane instead, the strains parallel to the fibers would be unchanged, except for the immediate vicinity of free edges. However, the strains perpendicular to the fibers would be amplified appreciably because the matrix is so much softer than the fibers. In the case of typical fiberglass-epoxy laminates, it was established in Ref. 3 that the transverse lamina strains would be on the order of five times as high as those in the fibers. Therefore, the constant-longitudinal-strain line in Figure 4, with a negative slope defined by the Poisson's ratio ν , would have the slope increased from -78.7° [$\arctan(5)$] for a fiber Poisson's ratio of 0.2 to -87.7° [$\arctan(5 \times 5)$] at the lamina level. This is so close to vertical that it explains the widespread success of the maximum-strain failure model used so extensively by the aerospace industry. The slopes of $+45^\circ$ and -45° associated with the equal and equal-and-opposite biaxial strain loci in Figure 4 would be increased likewise to 78.7° . Therefore, in a laminate containing 90° as well as 0° plies, the transverse strains in each lamina would be so severely restricted by the transverse fibers that *both* the failure models in Figure 4 would, for glass-fiber-reinforced polymers, be well approximated by the maximum-strain model applied at the lamina strain level, exactly as the author showed in terms of the Tresca criterion alone in Ref. 3. The match with the von Mises criterion with the maximum-strain failure model would be even closer.

The expansion of the failure envelopes in Figure 4, when depicted on the lamina strain plane, is shown in Figure 5, being close to the two vertical straight lines defining the maximum-strain model.

Fig. 5 The Von Mises And Tresca Criteria, Expanded For The Lamina Strain Plane

It should be noted that the Poisson's ratio ν for the lamina is typically about 50 percent greater than for the

isolated fibers, as shown. The use of any of these three models shown would yield essentially the same predicted lamina strengths. However, Figure 2 makes it clear that a carbon-epoxy laminates under biaxial loads. The failure envelopes for the fibers actually extend far above and far below the portion of the complete envelope shown because, in typical structural laminates, fibers oriented at other angles would restrict the transverse strains that could be developed in the lamina – with the transverse strains in the fibers being even less than in the lamina, focusing the effective portion of this failure envelope close to the uniaxial load line for the lamina.

postulate that the fibers failed by dilatation (brittle fracture) would yield a very different prediction for the influence of transverse strains (or stresses). More is said about this difference later, in the context of the test data for

THE STRAIN-INVARIANT CHARACTERIZATION OF FAILURES IN TRANSVERSELY ISOTROPIC CARBON FIBERS

The fundamental premise made *here* in regard to characterizing the strength of carbon fibers embedded in polymer matrices is that, in terms of *fiber strains*, there is *absolutely no difference* from the model used for glass fibers. The difference between longitudinal and transverse Young's moduli, and so on, creates differences in terms of *stresses*, as is to be expected.

The stress-strain relations equivalent to Equations (5) and (8) for isotropic materials are transformed slightly. Thus, with respect to the principal directions,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_1' \\ \epsilon_2' \\ \epsilon_3' \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{21}}{E_2} & -\frac{\nu_{31}}{E_3} \\ -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} & \frac{1}{E_2} & -\frac{\nu_{32}}{E_3} \\ -\frac{\nu_{13}}{E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{23}}{E_2} & \frac{1}{E_3} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1' \\ \sigma_2' \\ \sigma_3' \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (16)$$

in which transverse symmetry about the 1-axis requires that

$$E_2 = E_3, \quad \nu_{12} = \nu_{13}, \quad \nu_{23} = \nu_{32}, \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} = \frac{\nu_{21}}{E_2}. \quad (17)$$

Thus, for the customary 2-D case in which $\sigma_3 = 0$,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_1' - \epsilon_2' \\ \epsilon_1' - \epsilon_3' \\ \epsilon_2' - \epsilon_3' \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{(1 + \nu_{12})}{E_1} & -\frac{(1 + \nu_{21})}{E_2} \\ \frac{(1 + \nu_{12})}{E_1} & -\frac{(\nu_{21} - \nu_{23})}{E_2} \\ 0 & -\frac{(1 + \nu_{23})}{E_2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1' \\ \sigma_2' \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (18)$$

involving twice as many elastic constants for these transversely isotropic carbon fibers as were needed for the isotropic glass fibers.

Dilatational failure of carbon fibers is still characterized by Equation (1), in terms of the first

strain invariant. Thus,

$$J_1 = \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 \quad (19)$$

If such failures pre-empt distortional failures under uniaxial tensile loads, as is sometimes but not always believed to be the case for carbon fibers, J_1 would be related to the strain-to-failure ε_L^t by the following relation.

$$J_1 = \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 = \frac{(1 - 2\nu_{12})}{E_1} \sigma_1 = (1 - 2\nu_{12})\varepsilon_L^t \quad (20)$$

In the more general 2-D biaxial load case, still with $\sigma_3 = 0$,

$$J_1 = \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 = \frac{(1 - 2\nu_{12})}{E_1} \sigma_1 + \frac{(1 - \nu_{21} - \nu_{23})}{E_2} \sigma_2 \quad (21)$$

defining a straight-line relation on the fiber stress (and strain) planes. The effect of transverse stresses is amplified, with respect to the equivalent equation for glass fibers, by the greatly reduced transverse modulus E_2 . This line will not be exactly at -45° on the lamina strain plane for embedded carbon fibers, as it would be for isotropic glass fibers. Regardless of whether or not the fiber could fail by splitting along its length according some *other* failure mechanism, *this* relation can be *projected* to an intercept on the ε_2 axis, as shown in Figure 6. For a common critical value of J_{1crit} , the strains for a pure longitudinal tensile load in the 1 (fiber longitudinal) direction would be $\varepsilon_1 = \varepsilon_L^t = J_{1crit} / (1 - 2\nu_{12})$, $\varepsilon_2 = -\nu_{12}\varepsilon_L^t$. When $\sigma_1 = 0$ and σ_2 is critical alone, Equation (21) would predict that the critical J_1 condition would be reached when $\varepsilon_2 = J_{1crit} / (1 - \nu_{21} - \nu_{23}) = \varepsilon_L^t \times (1 - 2\nu_{12}) / (1 - \nu_{21} - \nu_{23})$, $\varepsilon_1 = -\nu_{21}\varepsilon_2$. Even though ν_{21} is much less than ν_{12} for carbon fibers, ν_{23} will be a little greater than ν_{12} , so the slope of this line is a little steeper, but close to -45° on the fiber strain plane, even for orthotropic carbon fibers.

Fig. 6 Dilatational Failure of Carbon Fibers under Biaxial In-Plane Loads, on Fiber Strain Plane

On the lamina strain plane, the slope of this line would be steeper, but not as much as for glass fibers. A typical transverse-strain amplification factor PAN-based carbon-fiber-reinforced polymers was calculated to be about 1.5 in Ref. 3. The corresponding slope would then be $-\arctan(1.5) = -56^\circ$, as shown in Fig. 6. This prediction has some very interesting implications. Assuming that the dilatation failure model is as applicable for fibers as it is for the matrix, this result implies that, if the fibers fail by dilatation, rather than by shear, the biaxial failure envelope on the laminate strain plane should exhibit this same sloping cut-off in the tension-tension quadrant. However, it *doesn't*, at

least not for the common carbon fibers used in the aerospace industry. The test results (Ref. 5) agree much better with the maximum-strain model, with a vertical characteristic for this quadrant, which is equivalent to *distortional* failures in the fibers, instead, just as Hart-Smith has maintained for decades.

Further experimental data, as yet inconclusive, concerns the nature of the fracture surfaces. Hart-Smith has seen photomicrographs of boron filaments with the classic fracture mirrors when embedded in an aluminum matrix, but cup-and-cone fractures and 45-degree sloping fractures when embedded in polymer matrices. He has published sloping and saw-tooth fracture surfaces for T-300 and AS-4 carbon fibers that could *never* be mistaken for fracture mirrors (Ref. 2). Conversely, he has been told that pitch-based carbon fibers *are* associated with fracture mirrors, as also are glass fibers. In short, unidirectional loads on unidirectional laminae have been associated with *both* brittle and distortional failures. This test, alone, is not sufficiently discriminating. Only the difference, or similarity, between strains-to-failure under uniaxial and biaxial loads would be unambiguous.

Turning now to distortional failures of carbon fibers, Equations (3) and (19) would establish a

critical shear strain, with respect to the principal strains, of

$$\gamma_{\text{crit}} = \sqrt{\frac{(\varepsilon_1' - \varepsilon_2')^2 + (\varepsilon_1' - \varepsilon_3')^2 + (\varepsilon_2' - \varepsilon_3')^2}{2}} \quad (22)$$

Since this criterion is applicable for all critical combinations of strains in the 1, 2, and 3 directions, one of the unknowns in Hart-Smith's earlier works on generalizing the Tresca maximum-shear-stress criterion to non-isotropic materials can finally be resolved. It was recognized that the critical difference between axial and transverse strains in the 1-2 and 1-3 planes had to be common because of the transverse isotropy of carbon fibers. However, Hart-Smith had postulated that the critical difference for the 2-3 plane could be different (but not less), since it was possible that different conditions prevailed. It is shown here, later, that this difference does exist, but that it is not arbitrary.

In the customary absence of stress in the 3 (normal) direction, the differences between (assumed principal) strains are

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_1' - \varepsilon_2' \\ \varepsilon_1' - \varepsilon_3' \\ \varepsilon_2' - \varepsilon_3' \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{(1 + \nu_{12})}{E_1} & -\frac{(1 + \nu_{21})}{E_2} \\ \frac{(1 + \nu_{12})}{E_1} & -\frac{(\nu_{21} - \nu_{23})}{E_2} \\ 0 & -\frac{(1 + \nu_{23})}{E_2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1' \\ \sigma_2' \end{Bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

It does not appear that expansion and grouping would simplify Equation (22) for non-isotropic fibers in the manner shown earlier for isotropic glass fibers. Nevertheless, it is possible to evaluate Equation (22) for the *separate* applications of pure longitudinal and pure transverse loads, in terms of Equations (23), assuming that the *entire* failure envelope is defined by distortion failures. For this exercise, the following values are used for the various Poisson's ratios; $\nu_{12} = 0.2$, $\nu_{21} = 0.02$, and $\nu_{23} = 0.3$. For a pure longitudinal load, in tension *or* compression in the 1 direction,

$$\gamma_{\text{crit}} = \frac{(1 + \nu_{12})}{E_1} \sigma_1 = (1 + \nu_{12}) \varepsilon_L^t = (1 + \nu_{12}) \varepsilon_L^c \approx 1.2 \varepsilon_0 \quad (24)$$

in which ε_0 is the reference fiber strain to failure under pure axial load in the 1 direction.

Under pure transverse tension or compression, the imposition of the same value of γ_{crit} can establish the corresponding critical transverse strains. Thus,

$$\gamma_{\text{crit}} = \frac{\sigma_2}{E_2} \sqrt{\frac{(1 + \nu_{21})^2 + (\nu_{21} - \nu_{23})^2 + (1 + \nu_{23})^2}{2}} \approx 1.185 \varepsilon_T^{t,c} \quad (25)$$

The assumption of a common distortional strain level implies a relationship between the longitudinal and transverse strains to failure *in the fibers*. This is

$$\varepsilon_T^{t,c} \approx \varepsilon_L^{t,c} = \varepsilon_0 \quad (26)$$

so that the transverse strain-to-failure of the carbon fiber would be very similar to, but not exactly the same as, the longitudinal strain associated with fiber shear failures under axial load, just as for isotropic glass fibers. At the lamina level, this transverse strain would be expanded by about a factor of 1.5 for orthotropic carbon fibers. However, since the Poisson's ratio of the unidirectional lamina is about 50 percent higher than for an isolated dry fiber, the straight line passed through these two extremes would still be at a slope of very close to +45°, exactly as the author has maintained earlier.

Assuming that Hart-Smith's model based on generalizing the Tresca criterion is realistic, the point at which the in-plane strains are equal and opposite according to the new invariant formulation would need to have a value equal or slightly greater than *half* the critical shear strain. This can be confirmed or refuted by combining the deformations due to the separate application of σ_1 and σ_2 stresses, with $\sigma_3 = 0$, with equal and opposite strains ε in the 1 and 2 directions. The corresponding strains in the 1 direction are then $(1 + \nu_{21})\varepsilon$, in the 2 direction $-(1 + \nu_{12})\varepsilon$, and in the 3 direction $(\nu_{23} - \nu_{12})\varepsilon$. The corresponding value of the equivalent shear strain would then follow from Equation (22) as

$$\gamma_{\text{crit}} = \varepsilon \sqrt{\frac{(2 + \nu_{12} + \nu_{21})^2 + (1 + \nu_{12} + \nu_{21} - \nu_{23})^2 + (1 + \nu_{12} - \nu_{21} + \nu_{23})^2}{2}} \approx 1.99\varepsilon \quad (27)$$

Given the value of ε_0 from Equation (24), the equal-and-opposite strain level is less than this;

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\gamma_{\text{crit}}}{1.99} = 0.603\varepsilon_0 \quad (28)$$

which is consistent with the corresponding values established earlier in this paper for glass fibers. It is also compatible with the value $(1 + \nu_{LT}^f)/2 = (1 + 0.2)/2 = 0.60$ used for the first author's generalization of the Tresca criterion.

Another useful check on this criterion is the corresponding strains for equal biaxial strains of the *same* sign, i.e. equal biaxial tension and compression. In such a case, the strains in the 1, 2, and 3 directions would be $(1 - \nu_{21})\varepsilon$, in the 1 direction, $(1 - \nu_{12})\varepsilon$, in the 2 direction, and $-(\nu_{12} + \nu_{23})\varepsilon$ in the 3 direction. The corresponding value of the critical shear strain would then follow from Equation (22) as

$$\gamma_{\text{crit}} = \varepsilon \sqrt{\frac{(\nu_{12} - \nu_{21})^2 + (1 + \nu_{12} - \nu_{21} + \nu_{23})^2 + (1 + \nu_{23})^2}{2}} \approx 1.40\varepsilon \quad (28)$$

from which the biaxial strain to failure is seen to be a little *less* than for uniaxial loads, given in Equation (24), because ν_{23} is slightly greater than ν_{12} .

These five ‘‘corner’’ points, at key locations on the fiber strain plane, are identified in Figure 7. This figure includes the ellipse defined by Gosse’s (and von Mises’) distortional failure criterion, passed through the uniaxial tension and compression load points. The equivalence is self-evident, even though the author must admit to an inability to precisely compute the amount by which the ellipse should be rotated to reflect the difference between the $\varepsilon_3 = 0$ plane, for which there would be no rotation, and the $\sigma_3 = 0$ reference plane used here. Hart-Smith’s shear cut-off on lines sloping at $+45^\circ$, as the method of generalizing the Tresca criterion to non-isotropic fiber is seen to be only a close approximation, but it is one that makes the further approximation of a corresponding slope of 45° for the truncated maximum-strain model on the *lamina* strain plane an *even closer* approximation for carbon fibers.

Fig. 7 Key Points on Distortional Failure Envelope of Carbon Fibers, on the Fiber Strain Plane

If the information in Figure 7 were replotted on the *lamina* strain plane, the strains in the 1 direction, parallel to the fibers would be unchanged, while those in the 2 direction, transverse to the fibers would be expanded by a typical factor of about 1.5, far less than was the case for glass fibers in Figure 5. However, since Gosse’s micro-mechanical models for post-processing the global finite-element analyses include the non-uniformities in both the matrix *and* fiber strains, it makes sense to conduct many such analyses parametrically and study the results before definitive statements are made about the most useful approximate way to approach these different trans-verse strains. It appears at this stage that there are 8 possible sites around the surface of fibers, at which distortion failures could occur, as well as 1 more site at the middle, many more than the 3 sites identified for the matrix (1 interstitial and 2 inter-fiber).

The bottom line is that, for distortional failures, adapting Gosse's invariant approach to fibers is numerically equivalent to Hart-Smith's generalized Tresca criterion. In addition, it adds two further features that had not been available before. The minor effects from applied shear loads that had previously been ignored can now be accounted for, by use of the complete expression for the critical shear strain. Also, the previously undefined difference between critical conditions in the 2-3 plane, with respect to the 1-2 and 1-3 planes can now be quantified, in terms of the differences between the various Poisson's ratios.

EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION OF THE DISTORTIONAL FAILURE MECHANISM FOR CARBON FIBERS

Figure 8 contains new test data that not only validate the authors' assertion that the *dominant* failure mechanism for carbon fibers is distortion, rather than dilatation but are also absolutely incompatible with the converse possibility. These represent tests on $\pm 10^\circ$ IM7/K3B coupons made from layers of unidirectional tape. What is significant about *these* tests is that the fibers failed first, without damaging the matrix. Because of an exceptionally high Poisson's ratio for a $\pm 10^\circ$ laminate, the fibers are subjected to transverse compression of an intensity almost as high as the axial tension developed in the fibers. And this can be achieved in a simple uniaxially loaded coupon, provided that it is long enough that no fibers extend from the grips at one end of the coupon to the other. It was found consistently

that the fibers failed in these coupons at longitudinal strains far *lower* than those developed in all- 0° (unidirectional) test coupons. This new test is very significant since, at larger fiber angles ($\pm 30^\circ$, $\pm 45^\circ$, and $\pm 67^\circ$), the equivalent angle-ply laminates fail in the matrix *without* damaging any fibers. In these other cases, the matrix does fail *before* the fibers could.

The new test results⁴, comparing the lamina strains at failure in 0° and $\pm 10^\circ$, show how good a model for fiber failures was Hart-Smith's original strain-based failure model at the lamina, rather than constituent level. The composite material was layers of unidirectional IM7/K3B tape, for which the stress-free temperature was established to be 460°F . The analysis performed here included full micromechanical modifications, to account for the different transverse strains in the fibers, matrix and laminae. The equivalent shear strain in the fiber was deduced as $\gamma_{\text{crit}} = 0.0195$ for the $(0)_n$ laminate, for which the lamina (and fiber) strain-to-failure was $+0.0181$ longitudinally. The associated transverse lamina strain was -0.0062 . For the $\pm 10^\circ$ laminate, the equivalent shear strain in the fiber *when the fibers broke*, with no prior damage in the tough thermoplastic matrix, was 0.0199 , showing agreement within 2 percent for the distortional fiber failure criterion. These tests were repeated several times to confirm that the results were accurate.

There was no agreement for the J_1 values, as would have been needed if the maximum-strain model had been governing. They were, respectively 0.0095 for the fibers in the 0° laminate and 0.0058 for the same fibers in the same matrix in the $\pm 10^\circ$ laminate. The longitudinal and transverse strains in the individual $\pm 10^\circ$ laminae, when the fibers failed, were $+0.0119$ and -0.0105 .

Fig. 8 Experimental Validation of Distortional Failure Criterion for Carbon Fibers, on the Lamina Strain Plane

⁴ One of our Boeing colleagues, Steve Christensen, deserves the credit for finally resolving this issue in his test lab. He repeated these tests several times to ensure that there was absolutely no possibility of matrix failures preceding those in the fibers, by microscopic examination of coupons loaded almost, but not quite, to failure.

Figure 8 also contains the original Douglas test results on in-plane shear of $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates, using a novel coupon described in Ref. 6, that started Hart-Smith along this road over a quarter of a century ago. The reduction factor is not exactly half; it is 0.6, which is a lot closer to 0.5 than to 1.0. While Hart-Smith's original lamina-level fiber-failure model is now known to be only a useful approximation, rather than a precise physical model, the measure of its accuracy is the simple formula

$$\gamma_{\text{crit}} = \pm(\varepsilon_1' - \varepsilon_2') \quad \text{for} \quad \sigma_3' = 0 \quad . \quad (29)$$

The new data give two estimates for this equivalent shear strain, at the homogenized lamina level, of $0.0181 + 0.00615 = 0.02435$ and $0.0119 + 0.0105 = 0.0224$. This agreement, to within 9 percent, versus 2 percent at the fiber level, indicates the improvement potential from modeling at the constituent, rather than homogenized lamina, level. These fibers failed at a far lower strain level in the $\pm 10^\circ$ laminates than conventional "wisdom" would have anticipated – and at almost precisely the strain level Hart-Smith predicted almost 20 years ago! Even better, unlike a pure-shear test on a $\pm 45^\circ$ laminate, it is not possible to blame the "low" test result on failure in the other, compressed, fibers with a lower strength than in tension. Neither is it possible to deny that the fibers broke *first*, even though none of them extended from one end of the test coupon to the other.

DISCUSSION

When Gosse's original matrix-failure model was first presented to him, only a few years ago, Hart-Smith could see considerable promise in the approach but could also see the need to differentiate between the fiber and matrix constituents. Like his own fiber-failure model, Gosse's matrix-failure model was originally formulated at the lamina level. Even so, it would clearly complement Hart-Smith's fiber-failure model, and vice versa. But there was room for improvement! In an astonishingly short time, in comparison with the history of research in this field, the two authors have built upon and combined their independent prior research into a single unified theory, complete with operational computer codes, that now covers all four possible failure mechanisms for both matrix and fibers and does so without violating any of the laws of physics. Its capabilities have been expanded tremendously during this co-operative effort. And, thanks to participation by some of the best experimentalists around the world, who generously shared their data, there is also considerable corroboration of the models. Indeed, it would not have been possible to complete these models without the guidance of credible test data that *any* meaningful theory had to be capable of explaining.

It is necessary to identify the specific load cases most likely to differentiate between the various theories, all of which are fitted to measured *uniaxial* lamina or laminate strengths. This is why, even though they are not used as input properties for any of the theories, it is the *biaxial* strengths, under loads of the same and opposite signs, that are the most discriminating. The focus of standards organizations on specimens used only for measuring reference strengths needed for *using* standard theories seems to have inhibited the development of test coupons for *other* loads, with which to *validate* the theories. The Douglas in-plane shear test results shown in Figure 8, a shear strength of 60 ksi for a $\pm 45^\circ$ laminate made from unidirectional T-300/N5208 carbon epoxy with a unidirectional lamina strength of 180 ksi, are still the strongest ever measured. For the cut-off in the 2nd and 4th quadrants to be imaginary, as so many established composite "experts" insist, there should be much higher test results, as shown in the lower-right corner. There aren't!

The other issue concerns the biaxial tension test data in the 1st quadrant. Swanson's data (Ref. 5) are consistent with the maximum-strain model here. For quasi-isotropic $(0/\pm 45/90)_s$ and $(90/90)_s$ laminates, they follow the rectangular failure envelope in Figure 9 on the strain plane. On the laminate stress plane, the biaxial strength of the quasi-isotropic laminate is 50 % higher than the uniaxial strength. It has been shown here that, for carbon fibers, these data are consistent with a *distortional* (shear) failure mechanism in the fibers, and *incompatible* with a dilatational (brittle fracture) failure mechanism. This is why no one has ever produced test data in the 2nd and 4th quadrants with equal-and-opposite tension and compression high enough to prove the absence of the cut-offs there. If the distortional fiber failure mechanism did *not* precede the theoretically possible dilatational failures, the tension-tension strengths would have to be far *lower* than the uniaxial strengths. One of the most significant outcomes of the current UK exercise on evaluating various composite failure theories (Ref. 7) is that, for the first time ever, an equal biaxial compression test has reached the strength predicted

